

A Look at the History of the Creation of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Annotation: This article, with an analysis of international experience, highlights the creation of the constitutional control department in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and then its transformation into the Constitutional Court, the formation of the court, the powers of judges based on historical sources and a comparative analysis of criteria and legal acts.

Key words: constitutional control, judge, council, official, law, resolution, decree, power.

Relevance. The Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the supreme judicial body exercising constitutional control and independently carries out its activities on the basis of law. The Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan considers cases on the compliance of legislative and executive acts with the Constitution. The powers of the Constitutional Court, its structure and procedure for its activities are established by Articles 132, 133 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law "On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan". This article covers the history of the formation and development of the constitutional control body, and then the constitutional court in the early years of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The study of the judicial system, in particular the history of the Constitutional Court, which is an important component of the history of statehood, is one of the urgent issues facing the science of history.

Research methodology. This article uses methods and techniques such as historicity, scientificity, systematicity, comparative analysis, historical-chronological, and reliance on numbers and evidence in specific historical contexts.

Research results. It is known from world experience that the main criterion for the emergence of constitutional control is inextricably linked with the emergence of laws, known as the Constitution. Constitutional control serves as a kind of guarantee for the implementation of the norms established in the constitutions [1, -P.167-168.]. First of all, it should be noted that any law, contract, court or state administrative body documents must comply with the state constitution. If a norm issued by state bodies contradicts the Constitution, then this norm will not have legal force and should not be applied, since it will be declared invalid [2, - P.46.].

When deciding which body should exercise constitutional control, the main attention was initially paid to the legislative authorities. Because they adopt the Constitution and play an important role in lawmaking. Also, in some countries, the actions of the executive authorities in this matter are also recognized as effective. In particular, this is evidenced by the fact that in some countries the heads of state have the right to refuse to sign laws adopted by parliament if the law submitted for signature does not meet the requirements of the Constitution.

Constitutional control is a verification of the compliance of a document with the constitution. When a law or other regulatory document is identified that violates the provisions of the Constitution, the Constitutional Control Body has the right to annul it.

Constitutional control is a special type of judicial and law enforcement activity in the state, which consists in verifying the compliance of laws and other regulatory documents with the constitution of this state. Constitutional control implies that the relevant state bodies and officials, when they identify a document that violates the provisions of the Constitution.

In most foreign countries, special state institutions are engaged in checking the compliance of legislative acts with the requirements of the constitution. It is the duty of these bodies to prevent the adoption of laws and other acts that contradict the constitution, and to prevent the application of such laws and other acts that violate the norms of the constitution if they have entered into legal force.

Measures for the legal protection of the constitution can be implemented by various bodies: the head of state, parliament, prosecutor's office, but currently in most countries judicial bodies have been established, the main function of which is to maintain and ensure constitutional legality.

It should be noted that the theory of constitutional control in its current form first appeared in the United States. For example, in 1803, the federal Supreme Court announced that it had the right to declare a moratorium on any laws that contradict the constitution adopted by the legislative body of the state. Thus, the third branch of state power, the judiciary, began to be engaged in the implementation of constitutional control. The courts have the power to suspend the implementation of normative acts adopted by the legislative and executive branches of government. Such control is currently in force in almost all countries with written constitutions.

Currently, in foreign countries, Constitutional control is carried out by the following bodies:

1. Courts of general jurisdiction. In the USA, Argentina, Denmark, Mexico, Norway, and Japan, the issue of the constitutionality of a particular law can be raised by any court of any instance. However, the final decision on this issue can only be made by the highest court. In a number of countries, Constitutional control is carried out only by the highest court of the state, which is the highest court of the state (for example, Australia, Bolivia, India, Ireland, Canada, the Philippines, Switzerland, South Africa).
2. Constitutional Court. In some countries, constitutional control is carried out by special Constitutional Courts, which are their main or only function. Such special judicial bodies are not part of the system of courts of general jurisdiction: (Austria, Germany, Italy, Spain, Turkey, Cyprus, Bulgaria). Such a system first appeared in Austria in 1920[3, -P.424].
3. By special agencies. In some countries it is carried out by a special body not related to the court. For example, in France there is a Constitutional Council, the composition of which is determined by the president and parliament. A similar system has arisen in some African countries - former French colonies.

It is no exaggeration to say that the Constitutional Court operating in Uzbekistan is a true equal to independence. The attempt to establish this court is one of the bold steps taken towards independence. On March 24, 1990, at the first session of the Supreme Council of the Uzbek SSR of the twelfth convocation, the composition of the Constitutional Control Committee of the Uzbek SSR was elected. A little later, on June 20, 1990, the Supreme Council of the Uzbek SSR adopted the Law "On Constitutional Control of the Uzbek SSR", which entered into force on July 1, 1990. According to Article 2 of this Law, Constitutional control in Uzbekistan is carried out by the Constitutional Control Committee of the Uzbek SSR, and in Karakalpakstan, by the Constitutional Control Committee of the Karakalpak ASSR [4, -P.28].

The Constitutional Control Committee of the Uzbek SSR was elected by the Supreme Council of the Uzbek SSR for a ten-year term, consisting of 9 members, including a chairman, deputy chairman and a

representative of the Karakalpak ASSR, from among experts in the field of politics and law[4, -P.28].

In order to ensure the consistency of the activities of the Constitutional Control Committee of the Uzbek SSR, its composition was updated by half every five years. This committee carried out control over the compliance of regulatory legal acts adopted by the authorities of the Uzbek SSR and the Karakalpak ASSR with the Constitution. The conclusion of the Constitutional Control Committee on the incompatibility of regulatory acts or their individual provisions with the constitution of the republic could be rejected by a resolution approved by two-thirds of the total number of deputies of the Supreme Council. It is clear from this that in the initial period the Constitutional Control Committee did not have much influence.

For the first time since independence, the powers of the Constitutional Court were reflected in the Basic Law. For example, Articles 107-109 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan set out the procedure for the organization and powers of the Constitutional Court. In particular, in accordance with Article 109, the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

1. determines the compliance of laws and other documents adopted by the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, government resolutions, resolutions of local government bodies, intergovernmental treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other obligations with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
2. It concludes on the conformity of the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the laws of the Republic of Karakalpakstan with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
3. It comments on the norms of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
4. It was stated that it will also consider other matters within the framework of the authority granted by the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan[5, -P.37-38].

On May 6, 1993, the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the Law “On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan”. This law went down in history as the first special regulatory legal act regulating the organization and activities of the Constitutional Court. Article 1 of this law stated that the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the highest judicial body of constitutional control in the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to the law, the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan is elected by the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, upon the recommendation of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, for a term of five years, consisting of 8 members, including the chairman of the court, his deputy, the court secretary and a judge representing the Republic of Karakalpakstan. According to Article 97 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the President who resigned due to the expiration of his term of office shall hold the position of a member of the Constitutional Court for life[6, -P.16-28].

High qualification requirements were imposed on a judge of the Constitutional Court. In particular, a citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan, who was a specialist in politics and law, and, as a rule, had at least ten years of work experience in the legal specialty, could be elected as a judge of the Constitutional Court. Each judge was elected in a separate procedure.

In accordance with the resolution adopted by the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 7, 1993, the powers of the Constitutional Court were temporarily assigned to the Constitutional Control Committee. The reason for this decision was explained by the fact that the composition of this court should be formed by the newly elected parliament - the Oliy Majlis. On this basis, the Constitutional Oversight Committee continued its activities until 1995[7, -P.48].

In December 1994, for the first time in Uzbekistan, elections to the Oliy Majlis were held on the basis of the principle of multi-party system. On August 30, 1995, the newly elected parliament adopted the Law “On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan” in a new edition. According to this law, the number of members of the Constitutional Court was reduced and it was specified that it would be elected

in a composition of five members, including the chairman, deputy chairman and a judge elected from the Republic of Karakalpakstan [8, -P.88-97].

The Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Jokargi Kenes of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Chairman of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Chairman of the Supreme Economic Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the Prosecutor General had the right to refer issues to the Constitutional Court for consideration. An issue could also be referred on the initiative of at least three judges of the Constitutional Court. The final decision of the Constitutional Court on the considered case was called a resolution, and all its decisions entered into force from the date of publication in the mass media. The decision of the Constitutional Court was final and could not be appealed. If new circumstances not known to the court arise in connection with the adopted decision, or if the constitutional norm on which the decision was based is changed, the Constitutional Court may reconsider its decision on its own initiative.

On the basis of the above law, the composition of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan was first elected by the Oliy Majlis on December 22, 1995[4, -P.29]. On July 5, 1996, the Procedural Code of the Constitutional Court and the Code of Honor of the Judge of the Constitutional Court were adopted in the form of Regulations, establishing the rules of conduct of judges.

In conclusion, the Republic of Uzbekistan, thanks to its independence, has achieved not only political and economic, but also legal independence in the literal sense. In order to build a truly democratic society, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted, based on the principle of separation of powers. For the first time, the independence of the courts and the separate branch of government were recognized in the Constitution of the sovereign Republic of Uzbekistan, and a constitutional court was established, having studied world experience.

REFERENCES

1. K. F. Gutsenko. Legal security organs. Textbook for educational universities and faculty. 2nd edition, ispr. and dop. - M.: Zertsalo, TEIS, 1996.
2. Constitutional law of foreign countries in questions and answers: Educational-methodical aid / Ed. A. V. Malko. - M.: Yurist', 2003.
3. Rustambayev M.Kh., Tukhtasheva U.A. Judicial and law enforcement bodies: Textbook. -T.: TDYUI publishing house, 2011.
4. Mustafojev B. Constitutional court: period of recovery, goals and tasks // Social thought. - Tashkent, 2002. - No. 6.
5. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. –Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1992.
6. New laws of Uzbekistan. Issue. 8. –Tashkent: Adolat, 1994.
7. Hakimova S. Organization and improvement of constitutional justice in the Republic of Uzbekistan // Bulletin of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan. –Tashkent, 2005. –№12.
8. New laws of Uzbekistan. Issue 11. –Tashkent: Adolat, 1996.